

THE IMPACT THAT ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND A FOCUS ON THE MARKET HAVE ON THE SOCIAL PERFORMANCE OF SOCIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

Marketing is a key indicator of company success, and it is often regarded as a factor in the sustained growth of for-profit and non-profit enterprises alike. Additionally, entrepreneurial orientation is a concept that has been studied extensively in the setting of commercial firms but has not been put to the test in the setting of social enterprises. In addition, there is no tried-and-true, generally recognised conceptual model of social enterprises available from the academic literature. The variables in this model would include entrepreneurial mind-set, market focus, and productivity. In order to fill this information gap, this research will examine how social enterprises' social and financial outcomes are affected by their adoption of different strategic orientations. Structural equation modelling was used to examine the hypothesised connections. Study results, based on applying the model to a group of 301 Portuguese community firms, show that social entrepreneurship and market techniques both have a significant effect on social performance. The results show that a social enterprise's market orientation mediates the effect of its entrepreneurial approach on its performance.

Keywords: Focused on social entrepreneurship, Innovation, Entrepreneurship, and Market Success.

1. Introduction

Thus, throughout the course of the previous decades, there has been an increase in interest from the general public, business media, and politicians in terms like social entrepreneurship, social entrepreneurs, and the social economy. This is largely because social enterprises play a pivotal role in promoting social change by offering novel, game-changing solutions to issues like ending poverty, enhancing the quality of the environment, strengthening social cohesion and community, increasing civic engagement, and generating economic growth (Defourny and Nyssens 2008; Yunus et al. 2010; Popoviciu and Popoviciu 2011). Although there is no agreed-upon definition of the phrase "social enterprise," it is generally believed to refer to a certain kind of business model inside which organisations are created with the dual goals of serving a social cause and becoming financially sustainable (Doherty et al. 2014). Since their stated purposes include both the development of social value and the pursuit for financial gain, we classify them as "hybrid organisations." It's also possible to classify them as public, private, or nonprofit (Kraus et al. 2017). Boards of directors for such organisations typically include representatives from a wide variety of stakeholder groups, as these businesses rely heavily on group dynamics in order to function. In contrast to the market-focused nature of social enterprises in Europe, new businesses inside the United States are often described as non-profits. While in Europe, new firms are more likely to be labelled as social enterprises. Volunteerism is highly valued by European non-profits. Conversely, in Europe, the collaborative natures of the enterprise and its associative and cooperative legal form have

traditionally gotten a great deal more attention. It's possible that the organisational structures of social companies might vary from one country to the next as a result of the varying welfare systems, civilised societies, social finance markets, and public policies present in each region. Businesses with a social mission are sometimes included in the "third sector" or "social economy," but the precise definitions of these terms might differ from country to country. This class includes nonprofits, co-ops, and other privately run enterprises not motivated by profit. Their contributions to society are undeniable, which is why it's so important to find ways to improve their performance. The social good, social value, and social impact that nonprofits seek to achieve are closely linked, making it difficult to evaluate them (Duque-Zuluaga and Schneider 2008). There is still no consensus on how to assess social performance; consequently, the above-mentioned paper is aimed at social entrepreneurs. However, several authors have presented techniques to measuring performance using the framework described by Bagnoli or Megali (2011) or Arena et al. (2015). Having an entrepreneurial mindset is a topic that has been studied extensively by academics interested in social companies. It has been stated that social businesses need to adopt an entrepreneurial attitude if they are to be successful in fulfilling their social missions (Schmidt et al. 2015). As a result, the typical traits (mindset and behaviour) of a successful father of the nation of a firm or organisation are highly correlated with the entrepreneurial attitude of the nonprofit organisation, which is reflected in the real experience of the participants (Covin as well as Wales 2012). The study was conducted in 2012 by Covin and Wales.

1.1. Entrepreneurial Traits and Social Enterprise Performance

According to trait theory, an individual's traits are indelible and unchangeable aspects of their character that have their origins in their biology and manifest themselves in their habitual ways of behaving and thinking. X. Ge, X. Tian, and C. Zhao (2022) these are the primary elements that influence an individual's actions. To cite this article: Bernieri, F. J.; Brown, J. A.; Fultz, A. A.; & Stosic, M. D. (2022) Promoting entrepreneurial traits is an effective way to predict workplace success. P. Nurmayanti, E. N. DP, and N. Indrawati (2022). The literature on entrepreneurial traits and related issues is organised around three fundamental tenets. A few examples are the "theory of major five personality traits" (which includes neuroticism, extroversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness, or openness), the "new trait theory," and the "three-dimensional theory" (which includes achievement objectives, locus of control, and risk-taking propensity) (incorporating human and social capital elements of entrepreneurs into the dimensions of personality traits). The age of business owners, their level of education, the duration of their work histories, and their job titles are just some of the variables that have been studied in an attempt to put a numerical value on entrepreneurial activity. Zhou, Y., Zhao, Y., & Sang, Q. (2019) took into account gender, age, first work unit, and major to increase the scope of the investigation of entrepreneurial attributes. Zheng (2004). Further, businesses, both public and private, are common Research subjects for Li, W.; (2013) or industrial technological corporations. This paves the way for research into the ways in which the personal traits of business founders and executives influence the development of new products and the growth of existing ones. Companies whose main objective is making money rather than assisting people have fundamentally different motivations and philosophies. Social enterprises, a novel

type of business wherein commercial value and social value coexist, compete with more conventional businesses while reinvesting their revenues into their social mission. Based on the work by Alter Wu, J., this study examines the traits of successful businessmen from two angles: compassion & experience (2008). Business owners play crucial roles on management teams, as they are the ones who come up with the ideas for new companies. Businesses, each with its own distinct character, may have difficulty choosing wisely when it comes to setting strategic objectives and making crucial business decisions. Hence, entrepreneurial traits are essential for a company's growth and prosperity. Having empathy means being able to put yourself in another person's situation and try to understand and cope with their feelings and problems. On the one hand, business owners that are emotionally invested in the well-being of their local communities' underserved members are in a better position to see the social problems that require fixing and provide for those people. They can expand their company's reach and effect change in these areas in this way. In contrast, entrepreneurs with compassion are more inclined to see things from the perspective of others with less power. When people have a strong motivation to help others, they are much more likely to start and sustain social businesses that provide services to underserved populations and generate social value. Owners of businesses often speak of their "previous experience," which they define as their accumulated knowledge, skills, and insights throughout the years of their careers. Previous studies have shown that entrepreneurs make managerial decisions for their organizations based on behaviours directly connected to their experience, which streamlines the decision-making process, increases efficiency, and eventually leads to greater business performance. The ability to reflect on and improve upon one's prior endeavours is a key factor in achieving corporate success and maximising productivity. Gabrielsson, Joseph (2011).

1.2. Relational Capital and Social Enterprise Performance

An organization's performance is directly tied to the amount of relational capital it possesses, which an advantage is gained via sustained interactions with its customers. According to the research of Yim et al., "relational capital" allows for the synergistic use of individual and collective expertise and resources to maximise overall effectiveness. It was published in 2013 by B. Yim and B. Leem. Social entrepreneurs make use of the relationships and contacts they already have in order to expand their reach and make new connections. If businesses have access to current information on changes in their industry or external environment, they will be better prepared to adapt to the changing landscape. Cullen et al (2000).s two-factor notion of relational capital states that a relationship's worth is determined by the mutual trust and dedication of its participants. Through open lines of communication and collaborative efforts, social entrepreneurs as well as the people they are trying to help are able to earn their trust and realise their goals. Because of this, social enterprises are better able to take on risks and work together transparently, which boosts their performance. High levels of trust inside a social interaction system can lead to decreased transaction costs, enhanced cooperation efficiency, and the promotion of mutual learning and/or common growth among members who specialise in different fields. If there is confidence between parties, more groups with shared ideals will want to join the current relationship network. The SP of social entrepreneurship can't be reached until all subjects are dependent on and helpful to one another, work together to solve

pressing social problems, and are motivated to create synergy. Their promise towards the world is reflected in the way their businesses operate as well as the relationships they cultivate. When people feel more secure and connected in their social interactions, they are more likely to work together. Building trust between parties facilitates collaboration across a spectrum of issues, saving time and resources for social enterprises. Unofficial codes of behaviour can fill a gap in formal institutions, and social entrepreneurs and other topics can work together to make this happen. Iiturrioz, C., for instance; (2015). By following the unwritten code of conduct, civil society organisations as well as other parties can more quickly resolve disagreements as head off future problems, preserving the continuity of collaborative partnerships and enhancing enterprise productivity.

1.3. Mediating Effects on Relational Capital between the Performance of Social Enterprises and Entrepreneurial Traits

One of the hallmarks of a successful social entrepreneur is a demonstrated capacity for empathy, which manifests itself in a willingness to put themselves inside the shoes of other individuals and find solutions to challenges from their point of view. As a result, their social circle expands and the other person is more likely to feel comfortable opening up to them. Entrepreneurial experience provides social entrepreneurs with such a foundation upon which to build the infrastructure necessary to maintain and grow their existing company. People are more likely to open up to successful businesspeople who already have a track record, giving them a leg up in terms of networking opportunities and access to more resources. Entrepreneurs in the social sector are particularly susceptible to this. Therefore, social entrepreneurs might gain from the expanded social circle that comes from having an entrepreneurial spirit. Just having an entrepreneurial spirit isn't enough; it's not productive and has little to do with how businesses really run. However, in order for social enterprises to benefit from their employees' entrepreneurial spirit, they must have access to adequate relational capital. When confronted with the real problem of limited access to outside funding, relational fund steps in with effective solutions for social firms and plays a pivotal role in elevating group output through individual entrepreneurs. The impact of interpersonal enterprises, the improvement of EP, and the realisation of their social worth are all stimulated by the entrepreneurial traits of their founders and leaders.

1.4. Regulatory Effects of Cognitive Legitimacy

One definition of legitimacy is the extent to which a person or group's activities are recognised as consistent with the generally accepted norms, values, beliefs, and definitions of society. Integrating both objective and subjective criteria for assessment, legitimacy as a perspective or assumption stands in for the information held by stakeholders about a certain organisation. The legitimacy of social and political supervision, overall legitimacy the political and social standards, and the legitimacy of an individual's own reasoning are the three categories of legitimacy identified by Suchman (1995). Research into legitimacy is motivated by a cultural system of belief, which is understood more uniformly by the academic community. This belief system is called cognitive legitimacy. To a large extent, the cognitive validity of a collection of beliefs depends on the extent to which it is seen as legitimate through other groups. When

compared to the other two types of legitimacy, cognitive legitimacy gives more latitude in the appraisal of stakeholders within groups or organisations when utilising objective evaluation standards. As a result, gaining the trust of those who matter most is less of a challenge for social entrepreneurs. Higher degrees of cognitive legitimacy have been linked to greater resource acquisition success in the past. Authors M. A. Zimmerman and G. J. Zeitz conducted their research in (2002). The cognitive legitimacy of a social enterprise increases when its stakeholders have faith in its competence or potential for growth and when they accept its mode of operation and business philosophy. There are currently no regulations in place in China for socially responsible corporations. Social enterprises frequently face the all too real situation of funding trouble because it is so difficult to accumulate sufficient capital. So, trust in the minds of consumers is crucial for social enterprises. Customers, governments, and the public at large all have positive things to say regarding social firms, which is consistent with a high level of cognitive legitimacy. Therefore, social firms' intellectual respectability can be viewed as a proxy for their ability to get recognition from resource owners and, consequently, gain access to extra resources that help them remedy the shortfalls originating from inadequate operational performance. However, for recently established social companies, cognitive legitimacy means increasing popularity; this in turn increases the likelihood that the public would support the businesses' commercial operations, which in turn increases the efficiency of those endeavours. Due to their low level of analysis, which results in less public support and support, and weak cognitive legitimacy, social enterprises are finding it difficult to obtain the relational capital essential to satisfy their survival and growth needs in the current environment? High-quality relational capital is crucial to the success of any business, and it is much easier to acquire for social entrepreneurs when governments provide regulatory backing and indeed the public is familiar with charitable firms.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Desiana, P. M., et al (2022) examined the social enterprise because the company's success depends on achieving not only its commercial and charitable goals (SE). However, there is scant information about the factors that determine SE's sustainability. This study implies that new methods are required for SE to thrive in the long term. To build on SE's history of innovation and sustainability, this study seeks to identify potential alternatives to the company's current sustainability strategy by considering the importance of adaptive capabilities, anticipating changes in the ecosystem, and managing internal resources. Based on the findings, external variables like the ecosystem and innovation are more important to sustainability than internal aspects like the company's strategy or culture. Strong but unfavourable correlation exists between dynamic capacity and long-term viability. Dynamic capacities have little effect on outside ecosystem components, while innovation is the only mediator between internal elements and sustainability. Ultimately, serial mediation between fluid capacity and novelty are essential factors in long-term viability. When dynamic abilities are employed to encourage creativity, stability increases.

Enthoven, M. P et al (2022) studied the social entrepreneurs and activists who have researched the shifting consumer culture can help bring about changes that improve the situation. This safe

harbour can protect cutting-edge sustainability solutions from the rigours of the market till they are ready for wider adoption. Here, we examine the tactics used by eco-friendly companies and activists to change consumers' mindsets. Our findings are based on in-depth interviews with 26 activists and social entrepreneurs operating in the Dutch market for quasi products, and we analyse the data with grounded theory. We find that activist efforts designed to dissuade unsustainable consumer behaviour are complimentary to the methods used by social entrepreneurs to attract customers toward sustainable purchases. These tactics have four parts: appealing with, contrasting with or expanding customers' ties to the values of environmentally friendly consumption; and a concentration on radical innovation. We show how the dynamic between consumer culture transformation programmes and niche-level sustainability transitions shapes the latter.

Maseno, M., & Wanyoike, C. (2022) studied have analyses the work of ten active Asoka fellows in East Africa. In particular, this essay describes characteristics of social businesses which help bring about significant shifts in the economic, cultural, or political circumstances faced by the poor as well as the marginalised. Hypotheses about fundamental innovations, management and operations, and expansion are developed by the most successful social enterprises. The article concludes with a discussion of the implications for future research, development, and use of social entrepreneurship. Organizations that distribute understanding and goods for free typically operate in multiple markets, while those that provide a free solution tend to function as charitable organisations or associations; organisations that help launch a new company's operations as charities, associations, as well as foundations; and organisations that sell products purpose as both social enterprises and for-profit businesses, according to the research.

Tian, X., Zhao, C., & Ge, X. (2022) proposed the social enterprises—a novel business model wherein public benefit and private profit coexist—have emerged as a key factor in the creation of innovative new forms of social government. But social enterprise growth in China is only getting started. While social enterprises' work has a major bearing on the development of social entrepreneurs and could even bring about novel benefits for the sector, the difficulties in enhancing the reliability that are all common for social entrepreneurs may impede their development. The impact of entrepreneurial abilities on the success of social enterprises has been largely overlooked in the many studies and reports on the subject of social enterprise performance. Our goal in conducting this research is to illuminate how entrepreneurial traits impact the growth of social companies in an institutional framework. In particular, the beneficial influence of entrepreneurial traits may be seen in both financial and social performance, and relational capital acts as a mediator between the two. Cognitive authenticity acts as a positive regulator of the connection among relational capital and economic performance. The results may enhance our knowledge of characteristics and inspire new approaches to help nonprofits make do with less money. Entrepreneurs in the social sector would do well to work on honing their own business acumen and forging proactive connections with other stakeholders if they are serious about increasing the impact of social businesses.

Beisland, L. A., et al (2021) researched the Microfinance social entrepreneurs have to live up to a certain set of financial and social expectations. Concern about microfinance institutions are losing sight of their initial social aim led to the creation of social rating organisations to increase the sector's dedication to ethical business practises (MFIs). Using a global dataset of 204 MFIs with social evaluations from 58 countries, we analyse which factors are most relevant in determining MFIs' socially performance ratings. Overall, we discovered that greater social ratings of MFIs were associated with increased financial success, extended service areas (especially in rural regions), well expressed social aims, dedicated workers, high-quality goods, and delighted consumers. Each of the social characteristics is given different weight by the various rating agencies, as we have seen. Greater transparency on the part of social rating agencies is needed so that all sorts of socially conscious investors, in addition to the central MFI, may compete on an even playing field. Recent attention in the microfinance industry has been directed toward moral concerns due to concerns that these institutions' original social objective has been watered down (a process known as "mission drift"). We argue that the recently introduced social performance evaluations contribute considerably to the discussion upon that ethics of microfinance. Rating agencies define social performance outcomes as objective assessments of how well a bank's goals align with commonly held social values.

Block, J. H., et al (2021) researched shows that impact investors' efforts have led to a rise in the number more social entrepreneurs who are able to raise funding. In this study, we analyse the criteria impact investors use to choose successful nonprofits. We conducted a conjoint analysis research on a pool of investment prospects and found that investors cared most about the venture's overall credibility, the social significance of both the problem it sought to solve, as well as its financial sustainability. We then assess the relative importance that different types of impact investors assign to these preliminary inquiries. We find that contributors, in contrast to debt and equity investors, place more importance on solving the social problem than on ensuring the long-term financial viability of the organisation. Also, the quantity of projects with full deployment is more highly valued by equity investors than loan investors. In addition to adding towards the growing body of information on impact investing, we present a comprehensive analysis of the commodity - linked currency types at work in this burgeoning sector and describe why impact buyers evaluate investing decisions. Both financial and social enterprises can gain useful insights from this.

Lin, Y. H., et al (2021) conducted the Social entrepreneurship issues have matured and expanded throughout the years, both in Taiwan and internationally. That's why social businesses are so unique: they combine for-profit and non-profit business models in order to accomplish their double missions of generating a profit and doing good. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine how corporate social responsibility, service quality, and brand image are interconnected. To examine the interrelationships between various variables of interest, the authors used a structural equation model (SEM). Findings show that social missions improve both service quality and brand image. Customers are more likely to feel compassion for a company if they identify with its social mission. Finally, the level of service offered mediates the effect of a social purpose on consumer attitudes about a company's brand. The management

of social companies may benefit from the study's findings regarding the relationship among social mission, service quality, and brand recognition.

Ridwan Maksum, et al (2020) studied the Micro-enterprises, the backbone of much more than 95% of all firms in Indonesia and the major source of earnings for 99.8% of all workers, play a crucial role in the growth of the Indonesian economy. However, many factors, including insufficient capital, skill sets, or technology, hinder small companies' ability to compete. The Indonesian government has implemented many solutions to these problems, but none have improved MSMEs' productivity or competitiveness (SMEs). An innovative approach employing a social enterprise was proposed by the Technology & Region Program of the Indonesian Academy of Science. Challenges faced by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are investigated through an analysis of the Iptekda LIPI socioeconomic method, which takes into account both societal and economic factors. Researchers in both East and West Javanese conducted interviews with company owners to gain insight into their expectations and experiences with this technique.

Spieth, P., et al (2019) considered that the only way to solve the massive problems facing our society today is to create new kinds of organisations that combine commercial and welfare institutional logics. Using the literatures of community-based and social-based business models, we analyse the examples of social entrepreneurs from either a business model perspective. This study, unlike others that have focused solely on commercial company models, is interested in the distinctive features and value creators of combined social purpose companies. We use a grounded theory approach and base our findings on interviews with leaders of several types of social enterprises. The characteristics of social companies lead us to propose four value drivers for social economic models: responsible effectiveness, effect complementarities, shared ideals, plus integration novelties. We highlight the practical implications of our research and provide a reference to the related literature on social business models.

Ramus, T., et al (2018) studied have examined the potential impact of both internal and external stakeholders on the innovation strategy of social enterprises, with the goal of fostering the development of novel goods, services, and collaborations that enhance the enterprise's or financial outcomes. The impact of competing interests on the adoption of inventions with real-world or societal benefits are the primary focus of this research. Our analysis of questionnaire responses from a sample of social organisations with an emphasis on work integration leads us to the conclusion that in times of disruption, administrative administrators have no significant influence on the innovation of the social organisation. However, it appears that the members of the board as well as other stakeholders do play a role. Our research contributes to the growing body of work in the fields of corporate strategy and ethics, as well as the study of how for-profit businesses can promote the development of social values alongside economic progress.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The design of this study is a survey that is cross-sectional, and it is used to test hypotheses about the correlations among entrepreneurial traits (ET), social enterprise performance (SEP), relational capital (RC), and cognitive legitimacy (CL). A questionnaire that was administered online and generated using Google Forms was used to collect the data. Participants were contacted through e-mail during the study. In the context of this study, the leaders and CEOs of Portuguese ethical businesses make up the population of interest for the study's target demographic. We were provided with a list of all 301 cooperatives that have responded in social enterprise performance, despite the fact that CASES did not have access to all of the most recent information at the time.

3.1 Data collection

In order to get this information, questionnaires are employed. A survey is a specific type of research tool that consists of a set of questions to collect information about respondents. The tool's intended use is for eliciting information from respondents. To get insight into a topic of interest, researchers conduct a census to compile data from a representative sample of the population. Because of their efficiency, low cost, and ease of administration, questionnaires are commonly used in research. One of the many reasons for their widespread acceptance is this. These tools are excellent for learning about a subject's habits, likes, dislikes, intents, attitudes, and beliefs and methods are to be applied in this.

4. RESULT

Table no: 1 Mean and rank of the social performance of social enterprises

Factors	Mean	Rank
Entrepreneurial Traits	4.58	2
Social Enterprise Performance	4.69	1
Relational Capital	3.78	4
Cognitive Legitimacy	4.05	3

Result: The performance for social enterprises was given the mean score of 4.69, which was the highest possible score. After that, the average score for the Entrepreneurial Traits section

is a 4.58, and it is a part of the category. The average score in Relational Capital is 3.78, which is the lowest possible value for this category.

Table no: 2 Cronbach’s alpha of the social performance of social enterprises

Factors	Mean	Overall mean	Cronbach’s alpha
Entrepreneurial Traits		4.58	0.748
ET 1	4.67		
ET 2	4.54		
ET 3	4.55		
Social Enterprise Performance		4.69	0.804
SEP 1	4.78		
SEP 2	4.87		
SEP 3	4.67		
SEP4	4.46		
Relational Capital		3.66	0.736
RC 1	3.67		
RC 2	3.56		
RC 3	3.76		
Cognitive Legitimacy		4.05	0.704
CL1	4.07		
CL2	4.05		
CL3	4.07		
CL4	4.03		

Result: According to this data, the dependability scores range from 0.704 to 0.804. The value of the Cronbach’s alpha reliable coefficient typically falls somewhere in the range of 0 and 1.

The highest possible value for Cronbach's alpha is 0.804, which represents the performance of social enterprises. It works out really well. After reaching 0.748, this score, which represents entrepreneurial traits, is considered satisfactory. The Cognitive Legitimacy category had the lowest score of 0.704.

Table no: 3 Pearson correlation matrix of the social performance of social enterprises

Factors	ET	SEP	RC	CL
Entrepreneurial Traits	1			
Social Enterprise Performance	0.765	1		
Relational Capital	0.657	0.546	1	
Cognitive Legitimacy	0.743	0.742	0.675	1

There is a positive correlation between entrepreneurial traits and SEP, RC, and CL, with respective correlations of ($r = 0.765$, $r = 0.657$, and $r = 0.743$). After that, there is a favourable association ($r = 0.546$, $r = 0.742$) between RC and CL and Social Enterprise Performance. Cognitive Legitimacy has a positive connection ($r = 0.675$) with Relational Capital, respectively.

CONCLUSION

This overview is timely, as research on SE has recently moved beyond questions of definition to focus on the study of the institutional and organisational processes involved in their creation and upkeep. Research on social enterprises draws on a wide range of disciplines, including organisational theory, management practise, social policy, psychology, ecology, and economics. In this survey, we adopted a multidisciplinary strategy to incorporate insights from these various areas. Scientists doing SE research today use a wide variety of theoretical paradigms, which really is indicative of the multidisciplinary nature of the field. The open innovation, value creation, morals, power, or social finance are all crucial areas for theory building, but still the top academic writings have primarily focused on extending institutional theory. Three major topics were covered: the why, the how, and the how to mobilise human resources. We looked at the major points of view and identified the most important unanswered question in each category. In a broader sense, we discover that: there has been a starting to emerge evidential basis regarding SE establishment and expansion in a variety of but not all, nations; SE discussion throughout different countries as well as settings is closely connected to political discussions but instead interventions; as well as SE literature certainly contributed to controversial topics regarding the significance of market place, gov't, as well as civil society in the provision of public goods around the world. Hybridist in organizations, management, and entrepreneurship has far-reaching theoretical implications for the study of management, and this research is just scratching the surface. Given the blurring of traditional borders between different types of organizations, it is important to examine the impact of having a dual or even a multiple mission on internal operations. While this review does a good job of critically analyzing the literature in this new field of management studies, there are three problems with the way the literature was identified for this study. Although the review method did incorporate articles from more heavily referenced journals, it did not include all of the relevant literature

from other sources. Second, qualitative research predominates among the publications, with some papers making important theoretical advances. While establishing statistically sound national and worldwide analyses is a top objective, quantitative SE research is still in its infancy. Managers of social enterprises also need expertise in resource acquisition, utilization, development, and improvement of organizational competencies, among other related skills. Unlike in the private and public sectors, SEs often makes strategic decisions based on social and ethical goals rather than financial ones.

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